

I.FAST

Innovation Fostering in Accelerator Science and Technology

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DELIVERABLE REPORT

Central information and contact point operational

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ABSTRACT

This milestone aims to deal with the organization and operation of a central information and contact point for industry and other external partners to access Technical Platforms (TPs) with the aim to ensure the dissemination of information, analysis of requests and contacts to the appropriate TP. This contact point can be made in different ways through the AMICI website, which is currently being updated. Two levels of contact are developed: a central contact through a general AMICI email address and a more specific contact for each partner at the addresses listed on each page presenting their technological infrastructures.

I.FAST Consortium, 2022

For more information on IFAST, its partners and contributors please see <https://ifast-project.eu/>

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Delivery Slip

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Executive summary

The central information and contact point is organized to allow external users to have a clear and updated information on the Technical Platforms available in the partners facilities and to easily reach them. The information is given on the AMICI website and the central contact point can be found on the website either by contacting the coordination team for global information on the AMICI collaboration or by reaching each of the partners directly by means of a specific email address indicated on each page presenting the technological facilities. Thanks to these specific addresses, the person or the group of person in the partner laboratory processes and responds to requests. Moreover, the coordination team will now be put in copy of the emails sent to all these addresses in order to keep track of all the requests received, to make statistics on the number of requests but also possibly relaunch partners who have not replied or forward the request to another partner performing similar services.

1 Introduction

Within Task 13.2, which is dedicated to developing and promoting services to industry in AMICI Technological Facilities (TFs), the goal of Sub-Task 13.2.1 is the organization and operation of a central information and contact point for industry and other external partners. The idea is that possible external users, from industry or academic laboratories, have clear and regularly updated information on the Technical Platforms available in the different partner facilities, can easily formulate a request for further information or for access one of the TPs, and get appropriate answers.

During the H2020 AMICI project [1], a web site was created and hosted by IFJ-PAN. It was containing a description of the technological facilities owned by the different partners. Contact points were given but there was no centralization of the requests and answers.

2 Central information and contact point

In I.FAST, the coordination team at CEA includes a project manager, who is the main organizer of the Central Information and Contact Point (CICP).

In order to be able to make the updates as easily and efficiently as possible, the AMICI website (<https://eu-amici.eu/>) had to be repatriated from our Polish partners' server to a server in France, hosted by the CNRS partner. Thanks to this manipulation, our project manager has now the possibility to make the necessary changes on the website itself, without going through incessant requests to the Polish partners. Due to this change in the hosting of the AMICI website, this milestone has been delayed by a few months. This delay will be compensated in the coming months by easier access to the core of the website.

2.1 CENTRAL INFORMATION

Central information is given on the AMICI website, which contains an updated description of the different Technical Platforms (TPs) available in the different partner facilities, classified by type of TP, so that a company or an academic laboratory can know which TPs could satisfy its needs.

2.2 CENTRAL CONTACT POINT

For external users, contact can be made in two ways:

- they can contact the coordination team in a general way through the general email address info@eu-amici.eu or, specifically for companies, industry@eu-amici.eu, that they can find on all the pages of the site, at the bottom of each page under “contact us”. By writing to this address, interested persons will be put in contact with the coordination team. They will be able to obtain global information on the AMICI collaboration and will be redirected to the most relevant partner(s) if their request concerns a specific TP or a specific type of TP.
- External users can also choose to contact the partner that has a TP of interest for him directly by means of a specific email address defined by each partner and indicated on each page presenting the technological facilities. Some examples are listed below:
 - CEA: amici@cea.fr
 - Desy: amici@desy.de
 - INFN: amici@sa.infn.it

These addresses refer to a person or a group of person in the partner laboratory responsible for processing the request and answer to the requester. The novelty is that, in order to keep track of all the requests received and their fate, **the coordination team will be put in copy of the emails sent to all these addresses**. This will allow to make statistics on the number of requests, the most requested facilities but also to follow the answers to the requests, and possibly relaunch those who have not replied or forward the request to another partner performing similar services.

This evolution on the contact point will allow us to be more efficient on how we communicate inside the collaboration and be more efficient in our responses to potential external users.

3 References

[1] AMICI – Accelerator and Magnets Infrastructure for Cooperation and Innovation – H2020
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Annex: Glossary

Acronym	Definition
AMICI	Accelerator and Magnet Infrastructure for Cooperation and Innovation
TF	Technological Facility
TP	Technical Platform